

MODERN METHODOLOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN PRIMARY CLASSES

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Annotation: Students will have to advertise the topic given in the handouts, the qualities of the person or object, actions, excerpts from the work, and role-playing instructions. Also, this method can be used to recommend poems, fairy tales, stories and other small works for reading lessons outside the classroom.

Key words: student, pedagogue, innovation, methodology, technique, education.

In fact, modern pedagogical technologies increase the productivity of the educational process, form the independent thinking process of students, increase enthusiasm and interest in knowledge in students, form the skills and competencies of solid assimilation of knowledge, free use of it in practice. In primary classes, where the child's thinking is being formed, it is very important for the teacher's skills, his skillful application of pedagogical technologies to the educational process, the search for new methods and methods of education, and the creative use of pedagogical experiences.

Morphemics is the doctrine of meaningful parts of words. Meaningful parts of the word are called morphemes. For example, the word "workers" consists of the parts "work", "chi", "lar" and "our". Each of these has its own meaning within the word. This is the last limit in dividing the words of our workers into meaningful parts. If these parts are divided again, its meaning will be lost. So, a morpheme is the smallest meaningful part of a word.

The linguist scientist Sh.Rakhmatullaev says that the morpheme is the main unit of construction after the lexeme and serves to express grammatical meaning, unlike the lexeme (Greek morphē - (form)).

Both a lexeme and a morpheme are equivalent to a part as a linguistic unit (linguistic unit). A lexeme passes to its full state and enters speech only after receiving a grammatical description from the point of view of its category. A morpheme is usually added to the lexeme of the category it belongs to. A lexeme is a leading unit, a unit to which a morpheme is added, a morpheme is a unit to be added to a lexeme.

A morpheme, like a lexeme, is an abstract unit: it is reflected as a symbol in the language memory part of the brain, and in this case it is called a linguistic unit. As a linguistic unit, a morpheme is a unity of expression and content. For example, the part -m at the end of the keldim unit is equivalent to a morpheme; the phoneme m serves as its expressive aspect; and the aspect of content consists of the meaning (attributing the I person to the unit).

The content aspect of a morpheme is the grammatical meaning it expresses. The content of a morpheme is simpler than the content of a lexeme: a lexeme is the name of a reality and performs a nominative function, while a morpheme does not have a naming function, but only a significant function: it expresses a grammatical meaning. The symbol of a morpheme in the state of a linguistic unit contains information about its expressive aspect and its characteristic features, as well as about the content aspect and its characteristic features. Every use of a morpheme is made by copying the symbol embodying this information; the representative of a morpheme that appears as a material unit as a result of such a process is called a morph and is called a speech unit. Therefore, it is necessary to distinguish between the status of a linguistic unit in the language memory part of a morpheme and the status of a speech unit as a pronunciation unit.

So, there is a physical similarity between a lexeme and a morpheme: in both, a phoneme serves as an aspect of expression, and both are equivalent to a part as a linguistic unit. Lexemes and morphemes differ significantly in terms of other important features. It is wrong to interpret a morpheme as a single language unit and a lexeme as a type of morpheme. If we agree with such a wrong opinion, then we support the opinion that the vocabulary stage of language development does not have its own independent unit. Such an idea is contrary to the study of the stages of language construction as a system. Lexeme - a unit belonging to the vocabulary stage of language construction, morpheme - a unit belonging to the morphemes stage of language construction; lexeme - lexical unit, morpheme - grammatical unit. A morpheme is the smallest linguistic unit used to express grammatical meaning. In the literature, a morpheme is defined based on language (more precisely, language) and speech. The first type of approach says "Morpheme is the smallest meaningful unit of language...". In this case, the morpheme is considered as a unit that makes up the structure of the language, but the word (water) is given as an example, and it is emphasized that this word is divided into the lexical morpheme of water and the additional (generalization, affixal, grammatical) morpheme -chi. , to the second type of approach

- returns to the idea that "a morpheme is a meaningful part of a word" that is, to evaluate a morpheme based on speech.

That's why introducing pedagogical innovations into the educational process, using pedagogical technologies in education, using various innovative methods and methods, and constantly seeking to increase the effectiveness of education has become the need of today.

It is known that today in the course of the lesson "Brainstorming", "Crossword", "Sinkway", "Muzyorar", "Case study", "Insert", "Venn diagram" and "BBB" technologies are used to organize the educational process. . In this article, we recommend several more innovative methods that serve to ensure the effectiveness and quality of the teaching process.

The "Advertising" method shows its effectiveness mainly in elementary school reading classes. This method can be used in the stages of the lesson process: asking about the passed topic and strengthening the new topic. In this process, the teacher gives the students handouts in the order appropriate to the essence of the topic, in which "Advertise!" the main rule is that the combination is written.

Pupils will have to advertise the topic given in the handouts, the characteristics of the person or object, actions, excerpts from the work, role-playing instructions. Also, this method can be used to recommend poems, fairy tales, stories and other small works for reading lessons outside the classroom. In this case, a student or a group of students recommends poems, fairy tales, stories and other small works of other genres for reading to other students. In the process of recommendation, various forms of advertising are used. The advantage of the "advertising" method can be seen in the following:

- the students' speech becomes more fluent, the skills of speaking in front of the team and freely expressing their opinion are formed;
- a meaningful organization of the lesson process is achieved, students' interest in the lesson increases, respect for books is formed in them, and their passion for reading works of art increases;
- pupils' outlook expands, healthy competition environment is created, respect for other people's opinion, listening to them carefully, concentration and thinking skills are formed.

"Pair of fingers" method is one of the effective methods that can be used in mother tongue lessons. The name of this method arouses the child's interest in performing it. The method can be

used at different stages of the lesson. For example, it is effective to use the number topic as homework in mother tongue classes. The "Pair of Fingers" method reflects the integration of native language and practical art. Students' fingers are used in the application of the method. In this, the teacher explains to the students to write numbers and counting words on the fingers of the right hand with the help of manual labor, and on the fingers of the left hand to draw pictures of people-things with the quantity indicated, and at the last stage, two when the fingers are joined, it is emphasized that there is a correspondence between the number and the indicated quantity. "Pair of fingers" prepared by the teacher in advance is shown as an example and explained by means of a picture: the left hand index finger has 2 numbers and a piece of paper written on it, the right hand On the index finger, a picture of an onion is drawn. When we put two fingers together, the word "Two onions" is formed. Continuing in this way, we draw pictures and write numbers on the remaining fingers.

Through the "Pair of Fingers" method, the following knowledge, skills, abilities and qualities are formed in children:

- the student's aesthetic taste is formed, his creative thinking increases, his interest in art and painting increases;
- the student's intellectual thinking ability is formed while the student's manual skills are developed;
- increases the interest of the teaching team in the lesson, encourages them to be active, and learns to what extent they understand the topic;
- student's interest in mathematics, art and technology, along with the subject of the mother tongue. Because, in the process of making "Pair of Fingers", the student draws, cuts and calculates and describes it on his fingers;

It is appropriate to use the "Rainbow polish" method for primary classes. This method can also be used in mother tongue, mathematics and reading classes. For example: when classifying words in mother tongue classes, classify words such as doll, car, laughed, cried, yellow, big, small, nine, and see words related to the noun group The task is to place the words of the adjective group on the blue line. This method can be used during the division of numbers into unit units in the mathematics lesson. That is, if we take the first color of the rainbow as a one-digit number, then the color of the second row can be an example of a two-digit number.

The following knowledge, skills, abilities and qualities are formed in children through the "Rainbow Shine" method:

- the student remembers the category of words by colors;
- students develop ideas about natural phenomena, they develop love for the environment and nature, and the skills to preserve it;
- pupils' worldview and scope of imagination expands, concentration, thinking, intelligence and resourcefulness skills develop.

The "Crossword" method is one of the methods that have been used for a long time, and we can find it in different textbooks of each class. In the preparation of crosswords, the Microsoft Word computer program, which is an information and communication technology tool, is mainly used. However, it can be seen that crosswords prepared using the Microsoft Excel program of the computer give more effective results than the previous ones. It is true that the Microsoft Excel program is a bit complicated and is launched on the basis of formulas, but it is a requirement of

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the time for teachers to acquire knowledge in the field of information and communication technologies.

Before completing the crossword prepared in the Excel program, it is possible to give ideas that encourage the students to complete the crossword and thereby increase their interest.

In the process of solving the innovative crossword, if the students answer incorrectly, our "smiley" will change to the form of sadness, if they answer correctly, you can see that the "smiley" is laughing. The advantage of the crossword is that checking the correctness of the answers given by the students is determined by a computer program and not by the teacher and appears on the screen. This ensures that the teacher's ability to evaluate students is increased and time savings are achieved. At the end, if all the answers are correct and clear, we can see words of praise for the students on the screen.

"Through the innovative "Crossword" method created in the Microsoft Excel program, the following knowledge, skills, abilities and qualities are formed in students:

- along with the knowledge related to the subject of the crossword puzzle, students will also develop knowledge about the science of "Informatics", become aware of the possibilities of information and communication technologies;
- students are interested in technologies, a wide desire to use them is formed, as well as information in classes
- the use of technologies increases students' interest in classes, improves the class environment;
- checking the correctness of the answers given by the students is determined by the computer program and not by the teacher and appears on the screen. This ensures that the teacher's ability to evaluate students is increased and time savings are achieved.

In conclusion, we can say that in the highly developing process of the information and communication system, it is very important for the teacher of primary education to have deep knowledge of techniques and technology, to be able to analyze them, and to be knowledgeable and skillful at the level of innovation. For this, in the process of organizing a lesson, he should choose and use methods that are understandable, easy and interesting for all students, use visual aids, apply newly developed technical tools, encourage students to work creatively and independently. It is desirable to use pedagogical technologies correctly and effectively. If the teacher is able to meaningfully organize the lesson based on creativity, the student's interest in science will increase.

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